

Email invitation

The text below is to be copied and pasted in an email to be sent to targeted potential participants including PREREview Community folks who have agreed to be emailed about Live Review events, as well as folks within the partner organization community.

Email Subject: Invitation to take part in our collaborative Live Review!

Email text:

Dear member of the [NAME COMMUNITY]

With this email, we would like to invite you to take part in a joint event hosted by [PREREview](#) and [INSERT PARTNER ORGANIZATION NAME].

We are joining forces to explore ways to improve the traditional peer-review process by engaging the research community. We hope you will take part in a community [Live Review](#) that aims to be open, time-efficient, scientifically rigorous, fair, balanced, and inclusive.

The Live Review will be hosted by two facilitators who will guide participants through a constructive discussion of the preprint following a curated template. The moderators will be joined by an invited expert, the author of the preprint, and researchers from all over the world including you!

WHEN: [ADD DATE AND TIME IN UTC]

WHAT: Join a 90-minute collaborative discussion of the following preprint

“[INSERT TITLE AND AUTHOR LIST]

[INSERT PREPRINT SERVER NAME AND PREPRINT DOI]:

WHERE: Zoom - [ADD REGISTRATION LINK]

WHO: Anyone interested in the research topic under discussion and armed with respect and a constructive attitude is invited to join

Please let us know if you would like to talk further or have any questions at community@prereview.org.

Email: Joining details

The text below is to be copied and pasted into an email to be sent to targeted registered participants for the LIVE Review.

Email Subject: Joining details for our collaborative Live Review on [DATE]

Email text:

Dear Participant,

Thank you for registering for our collaborative Live Review event on [INSERT DATE AND TIME] hosted by [PREreview](#) and [INSERT PARTNER ORGANIZATION NAME].

The Live Review will be hosted by two facilitators who will guide all participants through a constructive discussion of the preprint following a curated template. The event will last 90 minutes and yield a review based on the collaborative notes participants will jointly take during the call. The review will be shared and published on [PREreview.org](#) under a CC BY 4.0 license. Participants will have the option to sign the final review using their real name (via their ORCID iD) or via a pseudonym provided by the PREreview account.

WHEN: [ADD DATE AND TIME IN UTC]

WHAT: Join a 90-minute collaborative discussion of the following preprint

“[INSERT TITLE AND AUTHOR LIST]

[INSERT PREPRINT SERVER NAME AND PREPRINT DOI]:

WHERE: Zoom - [ADD REGISTRATION LINK]

PRIVACY POLICY

You can find additional information about how we handle your data in the [PREreview Privacy Policy](#) and [INSERT PARTNER ORGANIZATION PRIVACY POLICY].

CODE OF CONDUCT

It is our priority to ensure a safe, constructive, and brave discussion for everyone. This event is subject to the [PREreview Code of Conduct](#). Please review it before joining the event. Thank you!

If you have any questions please just reply to this email or contact us at community@prereview.org.

Email: Reminder

Email Subject: Reminder of PREreview and [INSERT PARTNER ORGANIZATION NAME] collaborative Live Review tomorrow, [INSERT DATE]

Email text:

Dear Participant,

This is a reminder that our collaborative Live Review event will take place tomorrow [INSERT DATE].

Our call will comprise of a guided 90-minute collaborative discussion of the following preprint:

[INSERT TITLE, AUTHORS & DOI]

Please ensure you read the preprint prior to the event.

Join us at [INSERT TIME] tomorrow at the following Zoom link: [INSERT LINK]

Any questions, just let us know by replying to this email or contacting community@prereview.org.

We look forward to seeing you there!

Best wishes,

Tweets/Toots/Other social media:

Registration is now open for the @PREreview_ & [INSERT PARTNER ORGANIZATION HANDLE/NAME] Live Review. Sign up here: [INSERT LINK]

[TAG RELEVANT COMMUNITITES] #reviewtogether

 @PREreview_ & [INSERT PARTNER ORGANIZATION HANDLE/NAME] joining forces to improve scholarly peer review! Join us for our next #livereview event on [INSERT DATE AND TIME] where we will be reviewing: [INSERT PREPRINT DOI]

[TAG RELEVANT COMMUNITITES] #reviewtogether

Want to join researchers from all over the world to improve a [INSERT TOPIC] Preprint?

Registration is now open for the PREreview + [INSERT PARTNER ORGANIZATION HANDLE/NAME] Live Review. Sign up here: [INSERT LINK]

[TAG RELEVANT COMMUNITITES] #reviewtogether

There's still time to join our @PREreview_ and [INSERT PARTNER ORGANIZATION HANDLE/NAME] collaborative #livereview!

When: [ADD DATE & TIME IN UTC]

What: [ADD PREPRINT DOI]

How: [INSERT REGISTRATION LINK]

[TAG RELEVANT COMMUNITITES] #reviewtogether

Slack

[PREreview](#) and [\[INSERT PARTNER ORGANIZATION NAME\]](#) are joining forces to explore ways to improve scholarly peer review! We hope you will take part in a community [Live Review](#) that aims to be open, time-efficient, scientifically rigorous, fair, balanced, and inclusive.

The Live Review will be hosted by two facilitators from PREreview who will guide participants through a constructive discussion of the preprint. The moderators will be joined by an invited expert, the author of the preprint, and researchers from all over the world including you!

WHEN: [\[ADD DATE AND TIME IN UTC\]](#)

WHAT: Join a 90-minute collaborative discussion of the following preprint

“[\[INSERT TITLE AND AUTHOR LIST\]](#)”

[\[INSERT PREPRINT SERVER NAME AND PREPRINT DOI\]](#):

WHERE: Zoom - [\[ADD REGISTRATION LINK\]](#)

WHO: Anyone interested in the research topic under discussion and armed with respect and a constructive attitude is invited to join

Please let us know if you would like to talk further or have any questions at community@prereview.org.